

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration and Carbon Sources on Wilt Diseases of *Rauwolfia serpentina*

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RAUWOLFIA serpentina Benth., commonly known as "Sarpagandha", is a well known medicinal plant in Chotanagpur. But due to wilt disease caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* its normal growth and yield are greatly affected.

The fungus *F. oxysporum* could grow well at pH 7.0 and out of ten carbon sources tested maximum growth was recorded at maltose.

The growth and yield of *Rauwolfia serpentina* Benth., is greatly affected by the destructive 'wilt disease' caused by "*Fusarium oxysporum*." The growth of this fungi and the formation of wilt disease might have a significant influence on the yield and medicinal value. It seems, therefore, a detailed study of *F. oxysporum* is needed. Physiological factors such as its response to variation in hydrogen-ion concentration and different carbon sources *in vitro* are discussed in this paper as pH and carbon sources play a great important role on fungal metabolic activities.

Materials and Methods

A pure culture of '*Fusarium oxysporum* (f)', isolated from wilted twig of *Rauwolfia serpentina* was used for this investigation. The growth of the fungus in relation to hydrogen-ion concentration and on different carbon sources were studied by growing it on Richard's medium. The liquid media was solidified with the addition of 2 per cent agar wherever needed. For each study at least three replications were taken.

The entire fungal mat was harvested by filtering over previously dried and weighed Whatman's filter paper No. 42. It was washed, dried and weighed. For sporulation study, the fungal mat was thoroughly mixed with distilled water and spores were counted in one drop of the spore suspension under low power of microscope. The degree of sporulation was based on the number of spores and are as follows: Excellent: more than 45; Good, 31 to 45; Moderate; 16 to 30; Poor; 1 to 15; Nil: 0.

To study the effect of pH, the medium was made

acidic or alkaline by adding N/10 solution of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide respectively. A pH-meter was used for determining the pH of the medium before and after the experiment. The growth of the fungus was studied under a range of pH 4.0-10.85.

For determining the effect of various carbon compounds, they were added singly to the basal medium by substituting the original corresponding compounds. The amount of the compound was so adjusted as to contain an equivalent quantity of carbon to that present in the basal medium.

Results

Effect of pH :

To study the effect of hydrogen-ion concentration, the media were fractionally sterilized by steaming them for half an hour on three consecutive days. Their pH was then measured and recorded as 'initial pH'. The final pH of each concentration was also taken at the end of the experiment. As the variations of the pH of the host leaf is not a major factor for the growth and sporulation pathogen, the pH of the host leaf is not taken accordingly. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON THE GROWTH AND SPORULATION OF *F. oxysporum*

Initial pH	Dry weight of mycelium in gm.*	Sporulation	Final pH*
4.0	00.00	Nil	2.45
4.60	00.00	Nil	2.65
5.00	2.84	Poor	2.90
5.55	5.92	Poor	3.25
5.90	8.00	Moderate	3.25
6.40	9.64	Good	4.50
7.00	12.37	Excellent	4.85
7.45	11.00	Good	5.95
7.90	8.73	Moderate	5.95
8.65	6.12	Poor	6.25
9.00	5.95	Poor	6.85
9.60	3.20	Poor	7.55
10.45	21.12	Nil	8.50
10.85	0.00	Nil	8.95

* Average of 3 replications.

Table 1 shows that *F. oxysporum* could grow over a wide range of pH, i.e., from pH 5.00 to 10.85. The maximum growth and sporulation both were recorded at pH 7.0, which was therefore taken as the optimum pH. No growth and sporulation were recorded at pH 4.0, 4.60 and at pH 10.85.

The pH of the medium shifted towards acidity and was nearly proportional to the dry weight of the mycelium in acid media, but it was not so in alkaline media. The more the mycelial growth, the greater was the change in pH in acid media and vice versa.

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Sugar in the basal medium was replaced with ten carbon compounds. In the present study, the rate of utilization of carbon compounds was investigated by recording the dry weight of the fungus. The result obtained was recorded in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that *F. oxysporum* was capable of utilizing carbon from different sources. It, however, differed in its choice for the best source of carbon for its growth and sporulation.

Maltose proved to be the best source of carbon for both growth and sporulation. While sucrose, fructose, rhamnose, lactose, galactose supported good growth and sporulation, the minimum growth of mycelium was recorded with raffinose and sorbose.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CARBON SOURCES ON GROWTH AND SPORULATION OF *F. oxysporum*

Carbon Sources	Average Dry weight of mycelium in mg.*	Sporulation*
D-Glucose	48.6	Moderate
D-Fructose	62.8	Good
D-Sucrose	58.1	Good
L-Rhamnose	54.5	Moderate
Lactose	51.9	Moderate
Maltose	69.4	Excellent
D-Galactose	60.3	Moderate
Raffinose	23.8	Poor
L-Sorbose	21.0	Poor
D-Xylose	32.9	Moderate

* Average of 3 replications.

Discussion

Hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium has a great importance on metabolic activities of the fungus. Commonly fungi cease to grow below pH 2.0 and beyond pH 9.0 by Wolf and Wolf⁶. Hawker² reported that the growth of *F. fructigenum* on Richard's medium of pH 4.6 gradually raised the pH until the reaction turned strongly alkaline. Sarkar³ reported that fungi *B. theobromae* could grow well at pH 6.5. Hawker² stated that most fungi grow best at neutrane reaction, that is pH 7.00. The present investigation also confirmed the same results in case of *F. oxysporum* which could grow best at pH. 7.0.

So far as carbon requirement is concerned, Bhatnagar and Prasad¹ reported that maltose is the best source of carbon for the growth and sporulation of *F. caeruleum* and *F. soloni*. Srivastava⁴ reported mannose as the best source of carbon for growth of *B. theobromae*. Sarkar³ observed that glucose is the best source of carbon for the development of papaya isolate of *B. theobromae*. But in this experiment it was observed that maltose is the best source of carbon for the growth and sporulations of *F. oxysporum* which causes the wilt disease of *Rauwolfia serpentina*.

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Chemical Investigation on Some Mangrove Species. Part I : Genus *Avicennia*

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THE *Avicennia* is a typical mangrove genus of the family *Verbenaceae*. The object of the present investigation is to ascertain the role of extrinsic factor on the secondary metabolites amongst the species in a genus. Literature survey on genus *Avicennia* revealed the presence of lapacol in *A. tomentosa*¹; betulinic acid, taraxerol, taraxerone and triacontane in *A. marina*². Present investigation deals with three *Avicennia* species, viz. *A. officinalis* Linn from Sundarban (West Bengal) and Kakinada (Andhra Pradesh), *A. alba* Bl. and *A. tomentosa* F. from Repalle (A. P.). The constituents isolated or detected from these species by standard procedures are listed in Table 1.

Experimental*

Extraction of stem bark of A. officinalis: Air-dried powdered bark (1.1 Kg) was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (5 litres) for 30 hr. The extract was concentrated and filtrated whereby a white solid (4 g) residue (A) was obtained. The filtrate on evaporation furnished deep yellow solid (B) material (4.5 g).

Treatment of solid residue A

It was dissolved in benzene. The dirty white solid, m.p. 280°, separated from supernatant liquid was purified through repeated crystallisations from ethanol. The compound was identified as a betulinic acid, m.p. 300°, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3350 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; MS: *m/e* 456 (M^+), 433 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 412 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CO}_2$). Acetate, m.p. 257°, MS: *m/e* 498 (M^+).

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used had b.p. 60-80°.